

Survey Questionnaire

1. Are you familiar with the concept of Industry 4.0?

- yes
- not sure
- no

2. What do you most associate the term Industry 4.0 with?

- industry based on automation and robotics
- new style of enterprise management
- autonomous manufacturing systems
- Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT)
- Big Data
- artificial intelligence
- high quality of products
- digital transformation
- high demands on employees
- continuous learning process
- additive manufacturing
- I have no opinion
- other (please specify)

3. Have you participated in seminars/workshops/training/lessons thematically related to Industry 4.0?

- yes
- no

3a. What was the thematic scope of the seminar/workshop/training/class?

- basic information about Industry 4.0
- information on possible applications of Industry 4.0 solutions/tools
- information on opportunities and threats on the labor market in the conditions of Industry 4.0
- solving a practical case study in the field of application of Industry 4.0 solutions/tools
- analysis of practical aspects of implementing Industry 4.0 solutions/tools (both technical and economic)
- practical contact with the use/handling of Industry 4.0 solutions/tools
- other (please indicate which ones?)

4. Have you undertaken a job/apprenticeship/internship in a company using elements of Industry 4.0?

- yes
- no

4a. How long have you been undertaking a job/apprenticeship/internship in a company using elements of Industry 4.0?

- up to 3 months
- from 3 to 6 months
- from 6 months to 1 year
- from 1 to 2 years
- from 2 to 5 years
- more than 5 years

5. How do you evaluate the phenomenon of Industry 4.0 in the labor market?

- definitely negative
- rather negative
- no opinion
- rather positive
- definitely positive

6. Do you perceive Industry 4.0 as a threat or an opportunity in the labor market?

- definitely a threat
- rather a threat
- no opinion
- rather an opportunity
- definitely an opportunity

7. Do you have concerns about the future that Industry 4.0 brings in the context of the labor market?

- yes, I definitely have concerns
- yes, I have some concerns
- no, I rather do not have concerns
- no, I definitely have no concerns

7a. What aspects would help reduce your concerns about the future that Industry 4.0 brings in the context of the labor market?

- inclusion in the study plans of more classes developing soft skills
- inclusion in the study plans of more classes developing technical skills (e.g. 3D printing, simulation, etc.)
- allowing to spend more time in real companies (more internships)
- creating conditions enabling work in studies (adjustment of the schedule of classes)
- organizing industrial visits
- participation in real projects related to Industry 4.0
- organizing additional (optional) training/workshops on Industry 4.0 solutions
- organizing seminars with Industry 4.0 experts
- others (please indicate which ones?)

8. Do you see a need in expanding your knowledge of Industry 4.0 in the current reality?
- definitely yes
 - rather yes
 - no opinion
 - rather no
 - definitely no
9. To what extent do you think you are prepared for the labor market in an Industry 4.0 environment?
- I am not prepared at all
 - I am slightly prepared
 - I am averagely prepared
 - I am well prepared
 - I am very well prepared

Characteristics of respondents

1. Please indicate your age:
- up to 18 years old (inclusive)
 - 19 to 22 years old
 - 23 to 26 years old
 - 27 to 30 years old
 - over 30 years old
2. Please indicate your gender:
- man
 - woman
 - I prefer not to answer
3. What year of study are you currently in?
- first year of engineering/bachelor's studies
 - second year of engineering/bachelor's studies
 - third year of engineering/bachelor's studies
 - fourth year of engineering/bachelor's studies
 - first year of master's studies
 - second year of master's studies
4. What mode of study are you following?
- full-time studies
 - part-time studies